

The role of values and emotions in user experience

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Abstract

This paper examines the element “the user” in user experience. Current literature suggests that perhaps the most important aim for design is not to serve our needs and help our goal achievement, but to give meaning to our lives. The goal of this paper is to broaden the user experience framework by conveying the relation of user-related elements to each other and their role in user experience. By reviewing the relevant literature from design, HCI, and consumer research we suggest a tentative conceptual description of the relationship between user values and emotions.

Conference theme: Values and Culture

Keywords: user experience, values, emotions

Introduction

It has been claimed that perhaps the most important aim for design is not to serve our needs and help our goal achievement, but to give meaning to our lives (Chapman, 2005; Heskett, 2002). However, the traditional usability paradigm in HCI has focused on task- and work-related issues (Hassenzahl, Tractinsky, 2006). The aim has been to understand human information processing and cognition in order to fulfil the needs of the user to reach some specific goals. However, it is increasingly clear that the uses of computing technology are reaching far beyond productive tools to support work to other aspects of human life, such as providing entertainment or rewarding social interactions, and addressing the concerns of society as a whole (Karat, 2002; Karat, Karat, Vergo, 2004). Hence, designers should design products that function and that are understandable and usable, but that also bring other aspects, such as joy, excitement, pleasure, fun, and beauty, to people's lives (Jordan, 2000; Norman, 2004). Design for user experience aims to satisfy human needs beyond the merely instrumental, and to focus on how to create positive experiences rather than just prevent usability problems (Hassenzahl, Tractinsky, 2006). Hassenzahl and Tractinsky (2006) recommend that in designing for user experience the emphasis should be on the examination of aspects that contribute to the user's quality of life. Thus the usability goals might not be the most important ones. With a similar idea, Karat et al. (2004) suggest that a closer examination of people and what they value in life can lead to a better sense of how to address their needs regarding the increasingly varied use of technology. Norman (2004) proposes that the emotional side of design may be more critical to a product's success than its practical elements: objects in our lives are more than mere material possessions because of the meanings they bring to our lives. Users acquire meanings, not objects; objects simply provide a way of perceiving the meaning (Chapman, 2005).

According to Heskett (2002, 4), design is "an essential determinant of the quality of human life", as basically everything in our environment is the outcome of human design. The outcomes of design processes, the end results, he argues, should be considered in terms of the interplay between the designer's intentions and the user's needs and perceptions. It is at the interface of the two that meaning and significance in design are created (Heskett, 2002). However, as Vyas and van der Veer (2006) point out, designers can never really design with the intention that users will establish the 'same' meanings that the designers are trying to convey. The emergence of meaning depends on both what the system provides and what the users bring to the interaction. Insightful knowledge of the user is therefore required.

"Know your user" has been the leading phrase in user-centred design. However, as technology becomes more pervasive, the distinction between a tool and a valued artifact becomes terribly

blurred. It is assumed that appearance and aesthetics will have an increasingly more important role in facilitating an emotionally satisfying experience for the user, as the specific goal the user has in mind when approaching technology will become more varied and less easily identified (Karat, 2002). In the design of technology the focus should be on creating a balance between different qualities, functionalities, and aesthetics. Hence, the motivation for this paper emerges from the need to understand more thoroughly the user-related factors in user-product interaction, beyond the instrumental, to non-instrumental needs. In this paper, we first explore a definition and different approaches to user experience in order to understand the key elements constituting an experience. Then we take a look at consumer research to find out what affects consumers' choice of products. Next we explore the reasons why a user becomes attached to a product. The aim of this paper is to identify user-related issues that need to be taken more carefully into account in designing for user experience. The goal is to broaden the user experience framework by conveying the relation of user-related elements to each other and their role in user experience, the emphasis being on user values and emotions.

Concept of user experience

A number of user experience studies have focused on introducing and explaining the elements influencing user experience. The main elements mentioned in the literature that need to be taken into account in design are the user, the product, the interaction between them, and the context in which the interaction takes place (e.g., Arhipainen, Tähti, 2003; Desmet, Hekkert, 2007; Forlizzi, Ford, 2000; Hassenzahl, Tractinsky, 2006). User experience is a consequence of a user's internal state, the characteristics of the system, and the context in which the interaction takes place (Hassenzahl, Tractinsky, 2006).

Perspectives on user experience

Hassenzahl and Tractinsky (2006) discuss three different perspectives that are emphasised in the literature on user experience. The first stresses the affective and emotional aspects of the interaction, the second addresses human needs beyond the merely instrumental, and the third deals with the nature of experience. The first perspective focuses on the role of affect and emotions as an antecedent and a mediator of technology use, or as a consequence of positive emotional outcomes such as joy, fun, and pride. The perspective of human needs beyond the instrumental focuses on more complete view by stressing aesthetic and hedonic aspects of technology. The multidimensionality enables linking product attributes with needs and values by e.g. means-end chains. The nature of experience perspective focuses on the situatedness, uniqueness, and temporality of technology use. This is highlighted with the fact that judgments about experiences and the experiences themselves are related but not identical. According to

Hassenzahl and Tractinsky (2006), these three perspectives are dependent on each other and together they provide a holistic view of user experience. None of the perspectives alone fully captures the essence of it.

Non-instrumental product qualities

To facilitate good experience, product features need to fulfil both the instrumental and task-related and non-instrumental and hedonic needs of the user (Hassenzahl, 2006). Hassenzahl (2006) argues the actual fulfillment of user needs, instrumental or non-instrumental, (when attributed to the product) is perceived as product quality. Mahlke, Lemke and Thüring (2007) propose a hierarchical model of non-instrumental product qualities. The three main categories are related to aesthetic (the product is appealing to the senses), symbolic (the product is communicative and/or associative to the user or others) and motivational (the product stimulates the user) factors. Aesthetic qualities are further divided to visual, haptic and acoustic dimensions, and symbolic qualities to communicative and associative factors.

Typology of user experience

Buccini and Padovani (2007) aimed to tackle the many-sided nature of user experience by establishing a typology of experience. In their study, six categories of experiences were created: (1) experiences related to the senses; (2) experiences related to feelings; (3) social experiences; (4) cognitive experiences; (5) usability experiences, and (6) motivational experiences. By pointing out different types of experiences in human-product interaction, the researchers believe it is easier to improve the positive ones and diminish the negative ones. However, although the typology is well grounded in theory, no practical advice on how to implement it in design is given.

User experience as meaning

Vyas and van der Veer (2006) argue that approaches to designing for experience often attempt to predict and rationalise certain human aspects, leaving more meaningful and critical subjective information unattended to. They have tackled the problem by conceptualising users' experience as the meaning or interpretation users construct during interaction with or through interactive systems. Their conceptual framework challenges designers to envision their designs in new ways by allowing them to assess social, cultural, and other non-technical aspects related to the technology. As meanings are socially and culturally constructed, the framework would allow designers to understand how users construct and associate a specific meaning with the system. In addition, meanings, being a subjective and spatio-temporal phenomenon, differ from

person to person and the context in which the system is used. The framework helps designers to envision the function, interaction, and appearance of the system with respect to the sensual, cognitive, practical, and emotional forms of experience. Through these different forms of experience users use their interpretation and sense-making skills to construct a coherent whole of the experience during their interaction with the system. The framework focuses on how meanings are constructed during the actual use of the designed system.

Summary

Based on the literature reviewed, it is clear that the product must fulfil needs beyond the merely instrumental to facilitate good experience. The product must therefore contain qualities from practical to aesthetic, symbolic and motivational. These qualities are anticipated to evoke related types of experiences in interaction; e.g. aesthetic qualities are hoped to evoke experiences related to senses, and symbolic qualities experiences related to emotions. However, the frameworks reviewed do not explain what kind of experiences are the most important ones. A better understanding of these questions can perhaps be gained by identifying the factors relating to product choice and attachment.

Factors influencing consumer choice and product attachment

In consumer research the factors influencing consumer product choice have been studied. One line of research has concentrated on human values. Schwartz (2007) states that values motivate people's behaviour to strive to attain a desirable goal; they serve as a standard or criterion to guide in the selection or evaluation of actions or things. Therefore, values can be seen as guiding principles in people's lives, influencing user behaviour to help in reaching the things that really matter to the user. In this sense human values may have an influence on what kinds of products consumers choose to buy.

Judgment of products

Allen (2001) studied how values influence preferences for products and their features and, hence, product choice. He discovered that consumers use not only rational attribute-specific, but also emotion-laden, intuitive, and holistic judgments of products or services. The latter type of judgment (based on the product's symbolic meaning) is directly influenced by the values the individual holds, unfiltered by the matter of product features. Individuals who value a comfortable life may seek out and in turn have positive attitudes towards objects that bring about a comfortable life (e.g. luxury cars or large homes). The results of the study indicate that values and emotions both have an effect on consumer choice, especially in a case in which non-instrumental qualities are more important than instrumental qualities.

Relation between emotions and values

Laverie, Kleine, and Kleine (1993) studied the connection between emotions and values in consumption experience for understanding post-purchase consumer behavior. They found a linkage between certain emotions and values. Typically, the emotions related to values are positive. For example, consumption experiences expressing hedonic values (e.g. fun, enjoyment and excitement) are associated with the emotions interest, surprise and enjoyment. However, the results of the study suggest that certain emotions are linked to consumption experiences that express different values; experiences that are valued because of their link to self are combined with interest and a negative emotion, fear. The label “self” in the study was a factor for values sense of accomplishment and self fulfilment.

In a study by Desmet, Hekkert, and Hillen (2004) the relationship between emotional responses to products and human values was researched, The aim of the study was to understand why a certain emotion is evoked by a product.. The findings imply that knowledge of the users’ values can be useful for predicting emotional responses to new design, as a relationship between the emotions evoked by the design and underlying human values was found. However, Desmet, Hekkert, and Hillen (2004) suggest that in order to understand how concrete aspects of a product are related to consumer aspirations, insight into the instrumental (more concrete) values is required (e.g. ‘communication’ or ‘honesty’ as being of instrumental value in creating a sense of belonging). The values included in the study were general, basic values. These values are terminal and abstract in nature (like belonging).

Product attachment

Even though the link between emotions and values has been found in the consumption experience and encounter with a product, we feel it is useful to explore what kinds of reasons users have for liking certain products they own. A useful concept in this is product attachment, which is defined as the emotional bond a consumer experiences with an object (Govers, Mugge, 2004). This definition implies that an emotional tie exists between the owner and his/her object and that the specific product has a deep and important meaning for the owner.

Govers and Mugge (2004) studied the influence of congruity between the personality of a person and the personality of his/her product (i.e. product-personality congruence) on product attachment. The results of the study show that people become more attached to products with a personality that is similar to their own personality than to products with a personality that is dissimilar to theirs. Similar personality associations between the products and the owner allow

him/her to show the world who (s)he is. Consequently, the product gains symbolic meaning for the owner, as a result of which the owner becomes more attached to the product.

In Wehmeier's (2007) study of users' attachment to their mobile devices, user-device attachment is reflected in the dimensions of perceived aesthetics (perceptions of the device's beauty and aesthetics), perceived symbolism (meanings attached to and portrayed with the device), and perceived necessity (device for communicating and socialising).

Russo and Hekkert (2007) identified five principles that trigger the experience of love in user-product interaction. The principles were identified through an analysis of the reasons why people experience love when interacting with products. The first principle states that people love to use products that interact fluently. Fluent interaction refers to an optimal experience, a mental (cognitive) state of operation in which the person is fully immersed in an activity that involves processes such as interpretation, memory retrieval, and associations ("flow"). The second principle states that people love to use products that hold affective memories and act as reminders of these memories. These objects are carefully taken care of and cherished. The third principle, the symbolic (social) meaning of the product, focuses on meanings that can be exposed to and/or perceived by others in a social environment. The fourth principle is the sharing of moral values; people love to use products through which they can share moral and ethical values. It is about a match between the product's and users' ethical and moral beliefs; it is a sense of being good to other people and to themselves. In addition, it enhances people's personal values. The last principle refers to the product's ability to gratify our senses; people love to interact with products that are physically pleasant.

Summary

According to the literature reviewed, consumer choice or judgment of a product can be explained by the values the user holds dear. Values are especially influential when the product serves non-instrumental needs. Then the judgment of a product is holistic and emotion-laden. In fact it is a question of good user experience. Positive experiences with a product lead to product attachment. The most important factors leading to emotional bonding with a product are the perceived aesthetics, the ability to relate perceived product values to one's own values, and to express self-identity by product meaning and associations, which leads to affective responses.

Discussion

The symbolic and emotion-evoking qualities of a product are clearly important to facilitate good user experience. According to Chapman (2005), designed objects and experiences provide a

tangible means for us to engage with the world on an existential level, and the potency of objects in symbolically designating our particular being cannot be overstated. That kind of fit for user products evoke emotions and strengthens the user's self-image. People like and get attached to products that feel "right", and provide means for the user to express oneself and things that are important for (s)he. Design for user experience is balancing between the instrumental and non-instrumental needs of the user. For instance, a person motivated to learn new skills might not appreciate too-explicit instructions. (S)he would prefer to resolve the problem by him/herself and would get annoyed if given help. Another person who appreciates ease-of-use would be happy for the help feature. Experience of the meaning affects the value the product provides for the user (Boztepe, 2007; Heskett, 2002). However, value for the user can be assessed after usage and experience of the product. The challenge in design is to understand how do different elements constituting the user experience relate to each other, and what elements are the most important to take into account in certain context.

Conclusion

In this paper we have endeavoured to convey the user-related factors that need to be taken into account in designing for user experience. Two factors seem to have a particular importance. Emotions have an important role in addressing good experience. The emotional reactions in the interaction seem to give an idea of what is important for the user. In addition, emotions can be seen as outcomes of user experience. If emotions are the outcome of user experience, values can be seen as its main driver; they guide human behaviour towards a desirable and preferable end-state. In order to attract users and to provide excellent user experiences, user values and emotions need to be taken into account when designing products. In the review of the literature, some evidence was already found. However, the next step in researching the role of values and emotions in user experience is to gather more empirical evidence of their linkage in different context.

References

- Arhippainen, L. and Tähti, M. (2003). "Empirical Evaluation of User Experience in Two Adaptive Mobile Application Prototypes". International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Multimedia, Norrköping, Sweden.
- Allen, M. W. (2001). "A practical method for uncovering the direct and indirect relationships between human values and consumer purchases". *Journal of Consumer Marketing* 18, 2, 102-120.
- Boztepe, S. (2007). "User Value: Competing Theories and Models". *International Journal of Design* 1, 2, 57-65.

- Buccini, M. and Padovani, S. (2007). "Typology of the experiences". DPPI Conference, Helsinki, Finland, August 22-25.
- Chapman, J. (2005). "Emotionally Durable Design: Objects, Experiences and Empathy". Earthscan Ltd, UK.
- Desmet, P. and Hekkert, P. (2007). "Framework of Product Experience". International Journal of Design, 1, 1, 57-66.
- Desmet, P., Hekkert, P., and Hillen, M.G. (2004). "Values and Emotions; an empirical investigation in the relationship between emotional responses to products and human values". European Academy of Design Conference, Barcelona, Spain.
- Forlizzi, J. and Ford, S. (2000). "The Building Blocks of Experience: An Early Framework for Interaction Designers". DIS Conference, 2000, New York City, USA, August 17-19.
- Govers, P. C. M and Mugge, R. (2004). "I love my Jeep, because it's tough like me", The effect of product-personality congruence on product attachment". Design & Emotion Conference, Ankara, Turkey. July 12-14.
- Hassenzahl, M. (2006). "Hedonic, emotional, and experiential perspectives on product quality". In C. Ghaoui (Ed.), Encyclopedia of human computer interaction. London: Idea Group, 266–272.
- Hassenzahl, M. and Tractinsky, N. (2006). "User Experience – a Research Agenda". Behaviour and Information Technology 25, 2, 91-97.
- Heskett, J. (2002). "Toothpicks and Logos: Design in Everyday Life". Oxford University Press, UK.
- Jordan, P. W. (2000). "Designing Pleasurable Products: An introduction to the new human factors". Taylor & Francis, London, UK.
- Laverie, D. A., Kleine III, R.E., Kleine, S. S. (1993). "Linking emotions and values in consumption experiences: an exploratory study". Advances in Consumer Research Volume 20, 70-75.
- Norman, D. (2004). "Emotional Design". Basic Books, NY, USA.
- Mahlke, S., Lemke, I. and Thüring, M. (2007). "The Diversity of Non-instrumental Qualities in Human-Technology Interaction". MMI-Interaktiv, 13.
- Russo, B. and Hekkert, P. (2007). "On the experience of love: the underlying principles". DPPI Conference, Helsinki, Finland, August 22-27.
- Schifferstein, H. N..J., Mugge, R. and Hekkert, P. (2004) "Designing consumer-product attachment". In: Design and emotion. The experience of everyday things. London, Taylor & Francis.

Schwartz, S. H. "Basic Human Values: An Overview".

<http://www.fmag.unict.it/Allegati/convegno%207-8-10-05/Schwartzpaper.pdf>. Visited 3.12.2007.

Thüring, M. and Mahlke, S. (2007). "Usability, aesthetics and emotions in human-technology interaction". *International Journal of Psychology* 42, 4, 253-264.

Vyas, D. and van der Veen, G. C. (2006). "Experience and meaning: Some underlying concepts and implications for design". *European conference on cognitive ergonomics: trust and control in complex socio-technical systems*, Zürich, Switzerland, September 20-22.

Wehmeyer, K. (2007). "Assessing Users' Attachment to Their Mobile Devices". *ICMB (International Conference on Mobile Business) Conference*. Toronto, Canada, July 12-13.